

The Unprecedented Connection Between Memory and Blood: Hippocampus, Bone Marrow and the Logic of Energy Coordination

João Carlos Orquiza¹

Summary

This conceptual theoretical essay proposes an integrated and innovative view of biological systems, connecting the hippocampus and the bone marrow from the perspective of the logic of energy coordination. Traditionally, the hippocampus is seen as the center of memory and learning, while the bone marrow is treated as the exclusive focus of hematopoiesis. This conceptual analysis challenges these paradigms by suggesting that both systems share a common principle of **continuous cell renewal** and **energy coordination**, necessary for the protection and sustenance of the **37 trillion cells** of the human organism. The proposal elaborated here is that life transcends entropy, establishing an organized energy system, where memory and blood act as interdependent mechanisms of **adaptation** and **protection**. The essay therefore proposes a new paradigm for understanding biological systems as an integrated unit of incessant interaction and energy coordination.

Keywords: Memory, Hematopoiesis, Hippocampus, Bone Marrow, Energy Coordination, Integrative Plasticity, Quiescence, Coordinated Energy, ATP, Cellular Interaction.

1. "Psychology Undergraduate, Universidade Positivo. Londrina/PR/Brazil. ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9619-9939>. Email: joao.carlos56@cs.up.edu.br

Introduction: The Logic of Life and Coordinated Energy

Since the dawn of science, life has been defined by the ability to organize in contrast to the natural disorder of the universe. The fundamental tendency of matter is **entropy**, a constant search for the state of maximum randomness and thermodynamic equilibrium, as established by Prigogine (1980). In this sense, inert systems dissipate energy without direction, resulting in disorder. However, life emerges as an **extraordinary phenomenon**, an outlier in this natural movement of the universe. Life not only organizes itself, but does so through a system of **coordinated and controlled energy**, resisting entropy by creating order in matter (Schrödinger, 1944).

In the human organism, this organization translates into the coordination of **37 trillion cells**, which interact incessantly, second by second, to ensure the maintenance of a functional and adaptive system. The development and permanence of life depend on this interaction and, mainly, on the **energetic coordination** between all cells. This essay, therefore, aims to explore the connection between two apparently distinct biological systems — the **hippocampus**, related to memory, and the **bone marrow**, associated with hematopoiesis — to propose that both share a common fundamental principle: that of energy coordination and constant renewal, in favor of the adaptation and protection of the organism.

1. A Premissa Central

The universe, broadly speaking, can be described in two fundamental states of energy:

1. **Random and Uncoordinated Energy:**

It characterizes inert systems that follow the laws of thermodynamics, dissipating energy in a disorganized way, without a clear logic of structure maintenance, leading to the tendency of entropy. These systems achieve an equilibrium where there is no organized structure, only dispersion. Examples include rocks, equilibrium gases, and inanimate objects (Prigogine, 1980).

2. **Coordinated and Controlled Energy:**

It appears in living matter as a unique phenomenon, where energy is continuously managed to ensure the maintenance and renewal of complex systems. Life breaks with randomness by establishing **coordinated energy systems**, which are fundamental to sustain processes such as the production and consumption of ATP in a high-efficiency cycle. This phenomenon is the key to understanding the difference between living and inert matter (Schrödinger, 1944).

The **logic of life** consists, therefore, in the creation of order, where energy is organized in order to maximize the **sustenance, renewal and adaptation** of cellular structures. The hippocampus and bone marrow are two practical examples of how this energetic coordination manifests itself,

ensuring that the **37 trillion cells** of the human organism function as an interconnected and self-organizing system.

2. The Logic of Living Matter

The logic of living matter is based on the ability to **coordinate energy**. Examples of this include:

- **Memory in the Hippocampus:** The renewal of neurons in the dentate gyrus of the hippocampus allows the integration of information in a dynamic and adaptive way. This neurogenesis is essential for the formation of new memories and the adaptation to new information, ensuring that the memory system is constantly updated and able to respond to changes in the environment. This continuous renewal in the hippocampus relies on coordinated and controlled energy to sustain processes of synaptic plasticity and adaptation (Eriksson et al., 1998).
- **Hematopoiesis in the Bone Marrow:** The continuous renewal of blood cells in the bone marrow ensures the efficient transport of oxygen and nutrients throughout the body, maintaining the **coordinated energy** necessary for cell viability. The constant production of cells such as erythrocytes, leukocytes, and platelets reflects a biological system that dynamically adapts to the body's needs, whether in response to hypoxia, infections, or increased metabolic demands. Hematopoiesis, therefore, is a clear example of

how coordinated energy enables the maintenance of homeostasis and the adaptive function of the organism (Pittenger et al., 1999).

3. The Purpose of the Essay

This essay explores the **hypothesis** that the **hippocampus** and bone **marrow** share a common logic of functioning, based on constant cell renewal and coordinated energy. This proposal implies that both systems operate under the same fundamental biological structure, which allows the organism to transcend entropy and maintain organization at a cellular and systemic level (Alberts et al., 2014). This essay aims to propose a **new paradigm** that replaces the fragmented understanding of biological systems, considering them as integral parts of an interdependent energy unit.

4. Relevance and Originality

The relevance of this essay lies in the proposal to challenge and restructure the current paradigm in biological science, which traditionally fragments systems into isolated units. The approach presented here suggests a new way of understanding life as a deeply integrated phenomenon, in which different systems operate in an interdependent manner to maintain energetic coordination and continuous cell renewal. The analysis of the hippocampus and the bone marrow demonstrates that

both, by sharing the logic of coordinated energy, are fundamental parts of the same adaptive mechanism, essential for the survival of the organism.

The originality of this work lies in the articulation of a concept of **integrated energy coordination**, where the production and consumption of ATP are seen as central points that connect fundamental biological functions. This coordination allows transcending the natural tendency to entropy, organizing energy in a way that creates order, sustainability, and resilience in the living system. By proposing that apparently distinct processes such as neurogenesis and hematopoiesis are, in reality, expressions of the same underlying principle, the essay challenges the fragmented view of biological systems and inaugurates a view that considers life as an interdependent and coherent whole (Schrödinger, 1944; Monod, 1971).

This innovative perspective can have profound practical implications. The understanding that memory and blood renewal are connected through the same energetic logic can open new paths for the treatment of neurodegenerative and hematological diseases. More than a theoretical concept, **energy coordination** and interaction among the 37 trillion cells represent a promising avenue for rethinking therapeutic interventions that seek to restore or maintain systemic resilience. Thus, this essay not only proposes a new conceptual model, but also aspires to inspire new strategies for scientific and medical practice.

5. The Role of Quiescence and Cellular Activity

From the moment of the zygote, the human organism carries a programming that defines cellular behavior:

- **Quiescence Cells (G0):** Some cells remain in a functional but metabolically active resting state. These cells play a crucial role in preserving the body's long-term stability, preventing the wear and tear associated with continuous division, and maintaining a reserve of functional capacity that can be activated when needed. Quiescence cells, such as certain neurons in the cerebral cortex, are critical to maintaining neural homeostasis and ensuring that energy is utilized efficiently (Cheung and Rando, 2013).
- **Cells Actively Dividing:** In contrast, most cells in the body are constantly renewing, fulfilling essential functions for the maintenance of the biological system. Examples include bone marrow cells, which are responsible for the continuous production of blood cells, and cells in the dentate gyrus of the hippocampus, which support the process of neurogenesis. This constant activity reflects the need for dynamic adaptation to environmental changes and the demands of the body. The continuous division of hematopoietic and neural cells exemplifies how central the logic of energy coordination is to ensuring the resilience and adaptability of the human body (Eriksson et al., 1998).

6. Constant Interaction Between the 37 Trillion Cells

Despite functional differences, all cells in the human body are intrinsically connected, participating in a complex system of interaction that sustains life:

- **Energy Coordination:** The maintenance of energy balance in the body depends on the collaboration between quiescence cells and actively dividing cells. ATP, as the main energy currency, is produced and consumed in a constant cycle that allows for the maintenance of cellular order. This coordination is essential to avoid disorder and ensure the viability of the biological processes that sustain life (Monod, 1971).

- **Systemic Homeostasis:** The dynamic interaction between quiescence cells and active cells is fundamental for the continuity of cell functioning and the organism as a whole. Resting cells provide a strategic reserve that can be mobilized in response to specific needs, while active cells ensure renewal and adaptive response. This continuous interaction allows the human organism to function in an integrated and resilient manner, maintaining a state of homeostasis that is essential for survival (Alberts et al., 2014).

Conclusion

This essay proposes an unprecedented connection between memory and blood, suggesting that both share the logic of continuous renewal and energetic coordination. The hippocampus and bone marrow operate as integrated systems of protection and adaptation, sustaining the incessant interaction of the 37 trillion cells of the human organism. The presented vision challenges the fragmented perception of biological systems, proposing a unified approach that considers life as a coordinated and interconnected energetic phenomenon.

Theoretical Impact

This approach redefines fundamental concepts of biology, suggesting that the human organism should not be seen as a collection of fragmented systems, but as a coordinated, interconnected energetic phenomenon. Energy coordination and cellular interaction are fundamental pillars for understanding life, offering new perspectives for understanding health and disease.

Next Steps

Future research should focus on exploring the molecular mechanisms that connect memory and hematopoiesis, as well as the role of coordinated energy in maintaining life. Exploring how the interaction between quiescence cells and active cells can influence the resilience of the organism and developing new therapeutic approaches for neurodegenerative and hematological disorders are promising paths for advancing this field of study.

5. Discussion

The following discussion focuses on the detailed analysis of the two systems in question – the hippocampus and the bone marrow – and their respective functions of cell renewal and energy coordination. The hippocampus, as the center of neurogenesis, is critical for the formation of new memories and continuous adaptation. This process is deeply interconnected with the body's ability to maintain a coordinated energy system, where the production and consumption of ATP allow for the synaptic plasticity necessary for learning and responding to external stimuli (Eriksson et al., 1998). The bone marrow, in turn, is responsible for hematopoiesis, constantly renewing blood cells to support homeostasis. The logic of coordinated energy that enables hematopoiesis is analogous to the hippocampal renewal process, suggesting that both systems share similar underlying mechanisms, which are guided by the organism's need for adaptation and maintenance.

The central point of the discussion lies in the concept that both memory and hematopoiesis are not isolated phenomena, but integrated parts of a unified biological system that depends on energy coordination. Coordinated energy, as opposed to random energy, allows hippocampal and bone marrow cells to renew and adapt as needed, ensuring the survival and functional optimization of the 37 trillion cells in the human body. This coordination is essential for the organism to transcend entropy, maintaining organization and the ability to respond to environmental challenges.

6. Conclusion

This essay proposed an integrated view of the hippocampus and bone marrow, arguing that they both operate under a common logic of continuous cell renewal and energy coordination. From this analysis, it is concluded that the human organism is able to transcend the natural tendency of entropy by maintaining a constant state of coordinated energy, essential for the protection and adaptation of cells. Memory and blood are seen not only as isolated functions, but as interdependent systems that ensure the maintenance of life in an integrated and coordinated manner.

The theoretical implication of this work lies in the possibility of reformulating our understanding of biological organization, proposing a new paradigm where cellular processes are seen as parts of a global energy unit. Thus, future studies could focus on investigating the specific molecular mechanisms that connect neurogenesis in the hippocampus and hematopoiesis in the bone marrow, exploring how energy coordination is maintained and adapted to respond to the body's demands.

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